

PRAGMATICS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10054322>

Abstract. Developed in the late 1970s, pragmatics is a subfield of linguistics that studies communication. It is the study of how people interact when using language and it explains language use in context including the effect that context has on an utterance, and the goals the speaker intends to reach through the choice of means of expression.

Keywords: pragmatics, syntactics, pragmatolinguistics, sociopragmatics

The word “pragma” is Greek and refers to activity, to do or to act, and if we want to define the concept technically, it is referred to as the study of language in use. The American philosopher C. Morris made use of the term in his semiotic study (1937) in which he found that semiotics consists of three branches in: syntactics, semantics and pragmatics. Syntactics deals with the rules that govern how words are combined to form phrases and sentences; semantics, the association between signs and the objects they signify. Morris (1938:6) thus gives his famous definition of pragmatics as “the study of the relation of signs to interpreters”, considering it as a branch of semiotics (study of signs and symbols) dealing with the relation between linguistic expressions and those who use them, and a branch of linguistics dealing with the contexts in which people use language and the behaviour of speakers and listeners.

As a matter of fact, pragmatics is the study of meaning of words, phrases and full sentences in a social context, unlike semantics which deals with the meanings of words that can be found in dictionaries, Pragmatics was labelled as a "wastebasket of linguistics"(Mey,1993:12), but after many years it has advanced from a wastebasket to a full grown field.

In Crystal's words (1985:240), pragmatics is defined as follows: “Pragmatics is the study of language from the point of view of users, especially of the choices they make, the constraints they encounter in using language in social interaction and the effect their use of language has on other participants in the act of communication”. According to this definition, Crystal tries to explain that in order to achieve a successful communication between individuals, there should be a repertoire from a certain code to be selected first, and there should

be a respect to social rules that constrain the way people speak, and at last, these choices should have consequences on the hearers.

The figure below will represent Crystal's definition of pragmatics:

Figure1 1.Components of a pragmatic study

Leech (1983:6) defines pragmatics as "the study of meaning in relation to speech situations"; on the other hand, Blum-Kulka (1997:38) states the following: In the broadest sense, pragmatics is the study of linguistic communication in context. Language is the chief means by which people communicate, yet simply knowing the words and grammar of a language does not ensure successful communication. Words can mean more – or something other – than what they say. Their interpretation depends on a multiplicity of factors, including familiarity with the context, intonational cues and cultural assumptions. The same phrase may have different meanings on different occasions, and the same intention may be expressed by different linguistic means. Phenomena like these are the concern of pragmatics.

Blum-Kulka here explains broadly what pragmatics deals with; she shows that pragmatics is more concerned with the meanings that words in fact convey when they are used, or what meanings the speaker intends to convey in producing certain utterances. She also makes a distinction between early and contemporary pragmatics, and according to her early pragmatics research focuses or deals with isolated utterances and words in contrast to contemporary pragmatics which analyzes extended sequences in texts.

In contemporary pragmatics, there is a great interest in cross-cultural features; it studies differences between cultures which resulted in another area of research known as "cross-cultural pragmatics". Among the investigations made in this area is CCSARP (Blum-Kulka and Olshtain, 1984; Blum-Kulka, House and Kasper, 1989), comparing requests and apologies in eight languages

and language varieties. According to Blum-Kulka (1997: 55), cross-cultural pragmatics uses two approaches of analysis.

According to Leech (1983), these approaches are: pragmalinguistics and sociopragmatics. They are defined by Leech (1983:10-11) as follows: Sociopragmatics is the sociological interface of pragmatics. ... The term pragmalinguistics, on the other hand, can be applied to the study of the more linguistic end of pragmatics – where we consider the particular resources which a given language provides for conveying particular illocutions.

Thus, from this distinction, it is understood that pragmalinguistics examines the linguistic manifestations in a given language that convey pragmatic functions, whereas sociopragmatics focuses on how social and cultural circumstances influence pragmatic performance.

All in all, pragmatics is interested in the study of the speaker's meaning, not in the grammatical or the phonetic form of utterances, and the influence a given context can have on the message.

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